

Gait Recognition using Fuzzy Ontologies and Kinect Sensor Data

Ignacio Huitzil^a, Lacramioara Dranca^b, Jorge Bernad^{a,c}, Fernando Bobillo^{a,c}

^aUniversity of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain

^bCentro Universitario de la Defensa (CUD), Zaragoza, Spain

^cAragon Institute of Engineering Research (I3A), Zaragoza, Spain

Abstract

Gait recognition involves the automatic classification of human people from sequences of data about their movement patterns. It is an interesting problem with several applications, such as security or medicine. Even low cost sensors can be used to capture pose sequences with enough quality to make a successful classification possible.

In this paper, we describe the use of fuzzy ontologies to represent sequences of Microsoft Kinect gait data and some biometric features relevant for the gait recognition computed after them, enabling more reusable and interpretable datasets. We also propose a novel recognition algorithm based on fuzzy logic that outperforms state-of-the-art methods for straight line walks. We also face the problem of the identification of unknown individuals that are not present in the system knowledge base.

Keywords: Fuzzy Ontologies, Gait Recognition, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

The problem of gait recognition consists of automatically classifying human people by analyzing data about their movement patterns. Gait recognition has many applications, including security (e.g. authentication and surveillance) and medicine (e.g. automatic support for the diagnosis of neurological diseases). Compared to other biometric measures for human recognition, gait has several advantages: it is non-intrusive, does not require any

Email addresses: ihuitzil@unizar.es (Ignacio Huitzil), licri@unizar.es (Lacramioara Dranca), jbernad@unizar.es (Jorge Bernad), fbobillo@unizar.es (Fernando Bobillo)

collaboration from the subject, involves less confidential data than other techniques (such as face recognition), and is relatively difficult to manipulate (i.e., simulating a different walking style that does not seem unnatural).

In the last years we have witnessed an increase in the number of low cost sensors to capture pose sequences. An example is Microsoft Kinect [12], a motion sensing input device originally conceived as a peripheral for video game consoles but used in many other applications, such as diagnosis of Parkinson's disease stages [16]. Pose sequences provided by the sensor could be used to compute biometric measures related to the human gait which could eventually be used for human gait recognition.

Although there is a notable effort in the gait recognition using Microsoft Kinect (see Section 3 for a detailed overview), existing approaches have some limitations in terms of reuse and interpretability of the collected data, as well as in the management of imprecise and incomplete data.

Existing approaches generate big amounts of data which are difficult to understand by a non-expert or to reuse between different applications. For this reason, we advocate for the combination of Semantic Web technologies to represent human Microsoft Kinect data and the biometric features for human gait motion analysis computed using them.

Rather than using classical ontologies, and because of the intrinsic imprecision of the sensor data, we propose to use fuzzy ontologies. This way, it is possible to replace precise values with more flexible fuzzy sets.

Furthermore, we propose to divide each sequence of gait data frames into steps, as in conditions with incomplete data, step data would be easier to be managed. We also propose a novel recognition algorithm of a sequence (i.e., recognizing its author) basing on the similarity between two steps (steps coming from training data and steps obtained at production stage of the system).

The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows¹ empirical evaluation, a discussion about linguistic summaries, and the discovery of new individuals:

¹This paper is a revised and extended version of [4], including a different design of the fuzzy ontology, details about the system (data capture, preprocessing, and feature extraction), a different gait recognition algorithm, development of a new dataset, a detailed

- We discuss how to use fuzzy ontologies to represent both Microsoft Kinect data and biometric features for human gait motion analysis and recognition.
- We build a novel system to compute gait recognition, discussing each aspect from data capture and preprocessing to the final decision making process.
- We build a new dataset with 91 individuals and provide fuzzy ontologies representing existing datasets and the new one.
- We propose and evaluate a novel classification algorithm based on the use of step segmentation (rather than on full sequences), fuzzy logic operators, and a voting scheme. Evaluation shows that it is a very competitive approach.
- We discuss the problem of the classification of new individuals, showing promising results.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides some background on fuzzy logic and fuzzy ontologies, and Section 3 overviews some related work. Then, Section 4 details the architecture of our system, the use of fuzzy ontologies for knowledge representation, and our classification algorithm. Next, Section 5 discusses an empirical evaluation. Finally, Section 6 sets out some conclusions and ideas for future research.

2. Background

This section provides some background on fuzzy logic and fuzzy ontologies. A busy reader might jump ahead to the next section directly.

2.1. Fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic

Fuzzy logic is widely used to manage imprecise and vague knowledge [40]. One of the key concepts is that of a fuzzy set. While in classical set theory elements either belong to a set or not, in fuzzy set theory elements can belong to some degree. A *fuzzy subset* F of a reference set X is characterized by a membership function $\mu_F(x)$ that assigns to each $x \in X$ a degree of truth in $[0,1]$. As in classical (or *crisp*) sets, 0 means no-membership and 1 full membership. The difference is that now an intermediate value between 0 and 1 denotes partial membership to F .

The definition of the membership functions is thus a crucial issue in fuzzy logic and fuzzy set theory. A typical example of membership function is the triangular function, depicted in Figure 1. Despite its simplicity, it is commonly used in real-world applications.

Figure 1: A symmetric triangular membership function

Operations over classical sets can be often generalized to the fuzzy case. In the fuzzy case, conjunction, disjunction, complement and implication can be computed by using a *t-norm* function \otimes , a *t-conorm* function \oplus , a *negation* function \ominus and an *implication* function \Rightarrow , respectively. The interested reader can find a formal definition of these functions in [18, 25]. Some examples of t-norms are the minimum and the Product.

Those logical operators are not the only relevant operators in fuzzy logics. More generally, *aggregation operators* are mathematical functions combining different pieces of information. An *n*-ary aggregation operator is a mapping $@ : [0,1]^n \rightarrow [0,1]$; some additional properties are usually required (see [33] for details). A typical example is the weighted mean with respect to a vector of weights $[w_1, \dots, w_n]$.

2.2. Fuzzy ontologies

An ontology is an explicit and formal specification of the concepts, individuals and relationships that exist in some area of interest, created by defining axioms that describe the properties of these entities [31]. Ontologies are a de facto standard for knowledge representation and have been successfully used in innumerable applications, but sometimes real-world knowledge is imprecise and vague knowledge, and classical ontologies are just not enough. As a solution, fuzzy ontologies extend classical (crisp) ontologies by considering several

notions of fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic [32]. Before going into the details, let us briefly recall the elements of a classical ontology:

- *Individuals* denote domain elements or objects. For example, `person21`.
- *Datatypes* denote elements that do not belong to the represented domain, but rather to a different domain that is already structured and whose structure is already known to the machine. Data values can be, for example, numerical values, textual, or dates.
- *Concepts* or classes denote unary predicates and are interpreted as sets of individuals, such as `Human`.
- *Properties* denote binary predicates relating a pair of elements. There are two types of properties: *object properties* link a pair of individuals, whereas *data properties* relate an individual with a data value. For instance, `hasFather` relates two human individuals and is an object property, while `hasHeight` links an individual with an integer number and is a data property.
- *Axioms* are formal statements involving these ontology elements. The available types of axioms depend on the expressivity of the ontology language, but some typical axiom types are the following ones:
 - *Concept assertions* state the membership of an individual to a class. For example, the fact that `person21` belongs to the concept of `Human` people.
 - *Object property assertions* describe the relation between two individuals. For instance, one can state that `person21` and `person55` are related via `hasFather`.
 - *Data property assertions* describe the relation between an individual and a data value. For example, it is possible to express that `person21` is 180 cm by relating `person21` and the number 180 via `hasHeight`.
 - *Subclass* axioms state that a concept is more specific (a subclass) of another one. For example, `Woman` is more specific than `Human`.
 - *Subproperty* axioms state that a property, or a composition of properties, is more specific of another one. For example, the composition of `hasFather` and `hasBrother` is more specific than `hasUncle`.

The interested reader can find a complete list of the OWL 2 elements in [11].

In fuzzy ontologies, the elements of an ontology are extended in such a way that concepts, relations, datatypes, and axioms are fuzzy. In particular:

- *Fuzzy concepts* and *fuzzy properties* are interpreted as fuzzy sets of individuals and fuzzy binary relations, respectively. For example, `YoungHuman` denotes the fuzzy set of young people.
- *Fuzzy axioms* express statements that are not either true or false but hold to some degree. For example, we can state that `person21` belongs to the concept of `YoungHuman` with at least degree 0.9, meaning that he is rather young.
- *Fuzzy datatypes* generalize crisp values by using a fuzzy membership function. For example, instead of considering the crisp value `180`, now it is possible to consider `about180`, defined using a triangular function. The former datatype is incompatible with the value `179.99`, whereas the latter one is not.

There is not yet an standard fuzzy ontology language, but *Fuzzy OWL 2* [5] can be considered as a de facto standard. Fuzzy OWL 2 consists of OWL 2 ontologies with annotations encoding the fuzzy information which is not directly representable in OWL 2. For example, it is possible to represent a fuzzy datatype by adding an annotation encoding the type of membership functions and their parameters using an XML-like syntax. For example, the fuzzy datatype `about180` can be defined as follows:

```
<AnnotationAssertion >
  <AnnotationProperty IRI='#fuzzyLabel' />
  <IRI >#about180 </IRI >
  <Literal datatypeIRI='&rdf;PlainLiteral' >
    <fuzzyOwl2 fuzzyType="datatype">
      <Datatype type="triangular" a="175" b="180" c="185" />
    </fuzzyOwl2 >
  </Literal >
</AnnotationAssertion >
```

3. Related work

This section summarizes the previous work on gait recognition using the Kinect sensor or on the use of ontologies to represent Kinect data.

Gait recognition and Kinect. There is a long history of research on the recognition of people through the gait using video recordings [6]. The release in 2011 of the Kinect depth camera has led to another approach to the gait recognition. Since then, several research papers have addressed the gait analysis for human recognition with skeleton data captured by a Kinect sensor.

We can find in the literature some prospective works that use their own datasets, with few individuals (usually less than ten), to investigate the possibilities of this technology. In this sense we can mention the approach of [30], where the authors observed promising results concerning person recognition using a Naive Bayes classifier and a simple set of features obtained from 9 people. Another work to mention here is the one in [20]. In that case the features are characterized as static (height, length of bones) or dynamic (angles of joints). Several distances were used between these features and finally a K -nearest neighbor (KNN) classifier [17] obtained around 80% accuracy for ten people. In [1] the authors use their own dataset with lateral recordings from 20 participants. They extract some vertical and horizontal features, use a KNN based method and obtain 92% recognition rate.

Other kind of proposals use broader datasets with 30 people recordings [21, 22]. In [22] a framework for gait-based recognition is proposed. The authors provide a new dataset captured from 30 people walking in a straight line. For each subject, the dataset contains five sequences (corresponding to 5 walks in front of the Kinect camera) captured in three separate sessions during the same day. The authors extract from the dataset 16 dimensional vectors that encode the direction of every limb using two Euler angles. Then use several dissimilarity tests and achieve 93.29% identification rate. Some steps further are taken in [21] with a new method for fusing information from Riemannian and Euclidean features representation that achieves 95.67% accuracy on the same dataset. Moreover, the authors provide a new dataset for gait recognition captured from 30 people walking in a straight line and using the more recent Kinect v2, dataset available on demand. There are 10 sequences for every recorded person. As far as we know, that is the only dataset available captured with Kinect v2. The authors obtained 97.05% accuracy on that dataset.

A different approach to the problem of recognition of people is addressed by [7]. Specifically, the authors address the problem of recognition from sequences with partial gait cycles, considered common at the airport security checkpoints. They use an own dataset with 60 distinct subjects and a hierarchical method for frontal gait recognition using Kinect depth and skeleton streams and achieve 66.67% accuracy.

An even more extensive dataset (90 people) of freestyle walks has been provided by [23], although it is not covered in this paper. Moreover, the authors propose a recognition method based on a KNN classifier with the Manhattan distance, applied at a frame level. The features used in this case are the relative joint positions with respect to a fixed joint, namely the spine base. They enforce the method with a new kind of features, the relative joint movement with respect to the same fixed joint, and achieve 96.8% accuracy.

The most extensive Kinect skeleton dataset that we found in the literature is described in [2]. The authors provide a dataset with lateral recording of the subjects. Each sequence represents a round of the subject in front of a Kinect camera on a semi-circle path. The Kinect camera was placed at the center of the semi-circle, on a spinning dish and was rotated to keep the subject in the center of the view. Several recognition methods were tested on this dataset, most of them based on the nearest neighbour [10] (KNN method with $K=1$) with Manhattan distance, with variations in the type of features used. In particular, [2] obtained 87.7% accuracy, [39] achieved 95.4% accuracy, and [23] reached 97% recognition rate.

Details of the features used by each related work can be found in subsection 4.2.4.

Ontologies and Kinect. There have also been some previous approaches to represent Kinect-related data using classical ontologies [14] and fuzzy ones [13]. The authors even developed the so-called *Kinect ontology*. However, despite this generic name, their approach is strongly focused on a different application, recognition of human activity, and cannot be reused in our scenario. On the one hand, *Kinect ontology* was not designed to encode the information directly obtained from the sensors. On the other hand, its fuzzy extension does not provide a fuzzy representation of the relevant features for gait recognition that we will discuss in Section 4.2.4.

4. Gait knowledge representation using fuzzy ontologies

This section starts by describing the architecture of our system. It has four main components as illustrated in Figure 2:

- a data capture phase that uses a Kinect sensor to obtain the skeleton data of a person walking. The settings used to build a new dataset are described in Section 4.1.
- a preprocessing phase, in charge to remove the data that were incorrectly obtained by the sensor or that contain too many inferred values, to segment the gait steps from a sequence of skeletons and compute the associated features (as described in Section 4.2)
- a fuzzy ontology to represent the imprecision of the values (as described in Section 4.3)
- and a decision phase to classify a sequence of gait steps, where each gait step includes several features described using triangular fuzzy membership functions (as described in Section 4.4)

Figure 2: Architecture of the system

4.1. Data capture

The Data Capture module interacts directly with the sensor and collects raw data from a Microsoft Kinect sensor. The Kinect sensor actually integrates several sensors (e.g., RGB camera, depth sensor, or infrared sensor) from which several joint points of the human skeleton are obtained. These joint points are retrieved as points in a 3D-space where the coordinate origin is located at the center of the Kinect sensor. For each joint point, the sensor also shows if the value is tracked or inferred. As an example, Figure 2(Data Capture) shows how a sequence of frames (skeletons) captured by a Kinect sensor could be. The skeletons capture the pose of a person during a walk. The joints of each skeleton are represented in the figure as red dots.

Kinect sensor has two versions: v1 (with 20 joint points) and v2 (with 25 joint points, as a superset of v1). In this module we use Kinect v2. It is worth to mention a more recent effort, NuiTrack,² with 19 joint points which are a subset of those in Kinect v2.

To capture the data, a sensor was placed in a hall at 1 meter above the ground. We designed a square-like path and asked the participants to walk in a normal way (as natural as possible) in a straight line direction and facing to the sensor. This is illustrated in Figure 3, where the solid line shows the path fragment that was actually captured by the sensor. A longer segment is not possible as the sensor is not able to capture closer or farther objects. The path was repeated 10 times, so we obtained 10 sequences for each individual, with each sequence including between 69 and 163 frames. Each sequence was physically stored as a different recording. The resulting dataset will be described more deeply in Section 5.1.

4.2. Data preprocessing

Next, the data captured in the previous phase are preprocessed. The Data Preprocessing module contains several algorithms for identification of gait steps, noise reduction, data alignment and feature extraction. This step does not require any human intervention.

4.2.1. Identification of gait steps

Our system uses a gait step-based identification approach rather than using entire sequences as other approaches do (for example [2, 39]). Sequence means in this context a

²<http://download.3divi.com/NuiTrack/doc>

Figure 3: Our data capture scenario

Kinect register of a person walking towards the camera. We consider a gait step as the sequence of frames (skeletons) from the moment when one foot strikes the floor to the other foot striking the floor. Usually, sequences contain 3-4 gait steps. In order to detect the gait steps in a sequence, a strategy based on local maximums of the distance between the feet time series in the X-axis (horizontal) and Z-axis (depth) is used. The frames (skeletons) registered from one local maximum (included) until the next local maximum (excluded) were considered as a gait step. Figure 2(Data Preprocessing) shows an example of two steps segmentation, where each gait step is represented by a set of skeletons.

4.2.2. Noise reduction

Each detected gait step is considered valid if only one foot is detected as moved. The movement of each foot is calculated based on its position in the last frame of the considered gait step with respect to its position in the first frame of the considered gait step. The frames corresponding to invalid gait steps were not considered for the next analysis steps. At this stage, frames with a large difference in length between limbs of the same type were also removed for further analysis. Specifically, frames, where the length of a bone differs by more than a third part of the average length calculated for that bone, considering all the frames of the gait step, are eliminated.

Some other strategies have been used for noise reduction purposes: based on height

of a person (we considered that a person can not measure more than 2.7 m), based on the distance in the frontal plane between legs (the separation between the ankles in the frontal plane should not exceed 1 m for a person who walks), and based on the variation of the movement direction in a gait step (the position of the spine base joint follows a fairly straight trajectory during one gait step; frames whose spine base joint is more than 0.2 radians of that trajectory have been considered noisy). Another possibility could be taking into account the percentage of inferred values in a frame, but this was not used in this version of our system.

4.2.3. Data alignment

Since the walking direction of a person may vary and is not always straight to the location of the camera, an angular rotation over the Y-axis (vertical axis) has been applied to each frame in order to align the skeleton joints with the hips position in the frontal (XY) plane. This kind of alignment it is widely used in the related work [7, 22, 23]).

A few features to be calculated (see next subsection) need a different alignment of the skeletons. Specifically, for the calculation of the length and width of the gait step, a rotation over the Y-axis (vertical axis) has been applied in order to align the skeletons with the direction of the displacement (direction computed based on the variation of the spine base joint).

Some of the related works use also a second rotation over the X-axis (horizontal axis) in order to align each skeleton with the position of the spine. This rotation may be useful when the Kinect camera is placed with a certain inclination toward the ground [7]. As in the recordings that we have used in this work the camera is straight, we have not applied that second rotation on the skeletons.

4.2.4. Feature extraction

Then, the features extraction is performed for each of the gait steps identified previously. Studying the related work, we have identified 8 types of features:

1. *Spatiotemporal features*: step length, step width, velocity and cadence. These kind of features were used in related works as [2].
2. *Anthropometric features*: height of the subject and length of each of the bones of the skeleton (head, up and low spine, left and right humerus, forearm, thigh, shin, foot and hand), computed as Euclidean distance of the corresponding adjacent joints. These

kind of features are commonly used in the related work on person recognition using Kinect, to compare with or to reinforce the performance of recognition based on gait kinematic features [2, 20, 39].

3. *Bones angles features*: angles of the projections on the XY, XZ and YZ plane of each of the bones corresponding to upper and lower limbs. Some of these features, generally related to the limbs position, were previously used in [2, 20, 22]. Additionally, we have computed the spine projection angles.
4. *Vertical distance features*: distance between a skeleton joint and the ground; e.g. left knee distance to the ground: $kneeLeft(Y)$. These kind of features were proposed in [1].
5. *Relative distance features*: distances according to the X,Y and Z-axis between symmetrical skeleton joints (e.g. right and left knees according to the X-axis: $abs(kneeLeft(X) - kneeRight(X))$) or between head and symmetrical skeleton joints; e.g. the position of the head joint with respect to both foots joints according to the X-axis: $abs(head(X) - (footLeft(X) + footRight(X))/2)$. These kind of features were used in [1] (X-axis distances) and [39] (some X, Y and Z-axis distances, selected with a greedy procedure - forward selection). In this work we have calculated the distances in all the axis, for each combination of joints proposed in the mentioned works.
6. *Relative joint position features*: position of each skeleton joint (25 for Kinect V2, 20 for Kinect V1) in X,Y and Z-axis with respect to a fixed joint of the skeleton, namely the spine base. These kind of features have been proposed in [7, 23].
7. *Connected joints angles features*: angles formed by different connected joints (e.g., the angle between the upper and lower left leg, formed by $hipLeft(X,Y,Z)$, $kneeLeft(X,Y,Z)$ and $ankleLeft(X,Y,Z)$). While this type of joint angles seems natural to take into account, it is not a type of features that has been commonly used for Kinect based gait recognition. Note that, to the best of our knowledge, these features had never been considered before in gait recognition using Kinect.
8. *Relative joint movement*: Euclidean distance showing the joint movement from frame to frame, with respect to a fixed joint of the skeleton, namely the spine base (e.g. the movement of the left knee: $EuclideanDistance((kneeLeft(X_i, Y_i, Z_i) - spineBase(X_i, Y_i, Z_i)), (kneeLeft(X_{i-1}, Y_{i-1}, Z_{i-1}) - spineBase(X_{i-1}, Y_{i-1}, Z_{i-1})))$), where i and $i-1$ represent two consecutive frames). These features have been proposed in [23].

We consider all the features used in the bibliography on purpose, as we want to propose a backwards compatible model. There could be some dependencies between features, but we still consider them separately as computing some of them from another features is not possible in general using standard ontology reasoning.

Table 3 summarizes the number of features of each type. All these measures, except the first type, may vary from frame to frame, thus we compute mean and standard deviation of them, for each detected gait step. It should be clarified that the mean aggregation usually characterizes the individual's pose while walking (except the anthropometric features where the average is a way to compute a bone length from different noisy values). For example, the mean of the relative position of the right foot joint on each of the axes would mean the average of the right foot pose during one step. On the other hand, the standard deviation aggregation usually characterizes here the amplitude of the movement. For instance, low standard deviations of the relative position of the right hand joint on each of the axes would mean that the individual does not move his right arm while walking. These kind of aggregations are commonly used in the related work at different levels: [39] considers them at a sequence level of the feature time series, [2] at a mixture between a sequence level and peak and valley level of the feature time series, [1] at a gait cycle level, and [7] at different fractions of a gait cycle level.

In this paper we propose the aggregation of the feature values at the level of a gait step, since even in conditions with short gait recordings, a gait step data would be easier to be managed than a complete sequence or a complete gait cycle with two steps (a gait step with right foot moving and another one with left foot moving). In an incomplete sequence scenario and splitting the gait cycle in four divisions, [7] has observed that the subjects achieved one or two divisions in 100% of the cases (one gait step would correspond to two divisions here).

Furthermore, as we will discuss later, the values of these features will be represented using triangular fuzzy membership functions. We have restricted to triangular functions because they are very simple (which makes it easier to compute the intersection of two fuzzy sets) and it is easy to compute them from an average and a standard deviation over all the frames that correspond to a step. Alternative fuzzy membership functions such as the trapezoidal or the Gaussian could also be considered.

Figure 4: Organization of our fuzzy ontologies: a schema ontology and several instantiated ontologies

4.3. Fuzzy ontologies for gait recognition

Our fuzzy ontology is able to represent raw Kinect data about the movement of a person but also biometric features computed from them. The former type of knowledge is represented using a classical ontological semantics, as we want to represent sensor data almost as they come from the sensor (only after some preprocessing, described in Section 4.2). The latter type of knowledge, involving our measures, is represented using some *fuzzy datatypes*. The idea is that in the future, other authors could reuse the raw data to compute new biometric measures.

Because of the huge amount of data we are trying to manage, we propose a distributed architecture formed by a general schema ontology, with the definitions of the classes and properties, and a collection of instantiated ontologies that populate the schema ontology with individuals and their attribute values. This architecture is illustrated in Figure 4.

The cornerstone of our architecture is the schema ontology. It contains 4 classes, 9 object properties, 391 data properties and 1409 logical axioms. The expressivity of the ontology is that of the Description Logic $\mathcal{ALCRIF}(\mathbf{D})$. To represent the Kinect data, we consider 4 mutually disjoint classes. For each instance of **Human**, there are several recordings. Every recording obtained using Kinect is represented as an instance of **Sequence** and each sequence is composed of several instances of **Frame**. After some preprocessing, we can also divide a sequence in several instance of **Step**, so that each step is related to a unique sequence. Each

step contains several frames, but each frame is associated at most to one step (if the human stops walking at some point of the video, there might be frames not associated to any step).

We also have object and data properties with their corresponding domain, range, and functionality restrictions. Relationships between classes are modeled using object properties `personIsInRecording`, `recordingHasFrame`, `recordingHasStep`, and `stepsInFrame`, together with their inverses `recordingHasPerson`, `framesInRecording`, `stepsInRecording`, and `frameHasStep`, respectively. Figure 5 shows the classes and their relationships. We use subproperty chains to infer missing information. For example, the chain `framesInRecording` \circ `recordingHasStep` is a subproperty of `frameHasStep`.

Figure 5: An excerpt of our ontology scheme.

Figure 6 shows a fragment of the data property hierarchy in the schema ontology. For example, we can see that `stepAttribute` contains the 8 types of biometric features enumerated in Section 4.2.4 plus some additional attributes (`otherAttributes`, with the moving leg and some IDs), all the four type 1 features, and both a comment and a range restriction on the functional property `velocityStep`.

We have an instantiated ontology for each gait sequence of each individual. Instantiated ontologies can be logically classified in a dataset, as we will describe in the next section. An instantiated ontology firstly imports the schema ontology and then populates it with individuals (persons, recordings, frames, and steps), and axioms (class/property assertions). The values of the data properties are fuzzy datatypes. In our scenario, fuzzy datatypes replace

Figure 6: Some properties (type 1) of our schema ontology

precise crisp values with a more general fuzzy membership function. For example, assume that we want to recognize an individual human001 using some biometric metrics, such as its average height. Rather than representing that the value of the data property meanHeight for human001 is 190 cm, we can take into account the imprecision of the sensor by considering instead a triangular function (see Figure 1) such that $\pm d$ cm is considered as acceptable. While one could consider using a better sensor, we aim at using low cost devices and thus must deal with such imprecision. To obtain such triangular functions, for each biometric measure we compute both the mean x and the standard deviation d . Recall that the values of the biometric features are computed for each step.

Each frame has 25 data properties linking it with each of the 25 joints identified by the Kinect V2 sensor. For example, sensor0 related a frame with a real number (xsd:decimal). The names of these data properties use the common numeration of the joints, but the ontology schema also has 25 equivalent data properties with more readable names. For example,

spineBase is equivalent to sensor0. To represent Kinect V1 or Nuitrack data, one would only use the relevant 20 or 19 (respectively) properties.

Regarding the biometric features, each step has several data properties, such as meanHeight (average value of the height of a person), or meanThighRightXZ (average value of the angles formed by the right thigh). Similarly, our ontology also allows representing biometric features of a sequence (although we do not currently use them) such as the total cadence (cadenceTotal, number of steps per unit of time).

As discussed in Section 3, none of the existing ontologies is suitable for our needs, so we needed to develop our ontology from scratch. It has been developed using Protégé [28] ontology editor. Classes, properties, individuals, and most of the axioms are represented as usual. To represent the fuzzy datatypes, we have used Protégé plug-in called *Fuzzy OWL 2* that can be used to create and edit fuzzy ontologies [5].³ The idea is to use a classical OWL 2 ontology with OWL 2 annotations to add the fuzzy information that OWL 2 cannot directly encode. The plug-in makes the annotations syntax transparent to the users.

The main version of the ontologies is encoded in OWL 2 Manchester syntax [36], but we also experimented with another version in RDF [35] using Turtle syntax (TTL format) [37]. RDF triples are appropriate to answer SPARQL queries [29], but this is not necessary in our gait recognition scenario.

Before concluding this section, let us illustrate how our approach leads to more readable datasets than the related work. Figure 7 (a) shows a fragment of a file included in the dataset built by Kastaniotis et al. [22], whereas Figure 7 (b) shows how one of our instantiated fuzzy ontologies represent some of the same data (the first four rows), corresponding to the first frame of the first recording of the twenty-first person.

4.4. Decision: gait recognition algorithm

The final step of our system is a Decision Module to classify a sequence of steps, where each step includes several features described using triangular fuzzy membership functions. Before that, we need to define the similarity between pairs of features, and pairs of steps. After describing our algorithm, we will extend it to deal with new individuals that do not

³<http://webdiis.unizar.es/~fbobillo/fuzzyOWL2>

Figure 7: (a) Original representation; (b) Fuzzy ontology representation

appear in the training set.

Similarity between two features. Give two features $f_1 = tri(a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{13})$ and $f_2 = tri(a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{23})$, we propose several ways to compute its similarity $s(f_1, f_2)$. Firstly, we can compute the degree of satisfaction of both restrictions by taking the intersection of the two fuzzy sets and then defuzzifying it into a single value, i.e., given the intersection set $f_1 \cap f_2$ characterized by its membership function $\mu_{f_1 \cap f_2}(x) = \mu_{f_1}(x) \otimes \mu_{f_2}(x)$, where $\mu_f(x)$ denotes the membership degree of x to the triangular fuzzy function associated to the feature f :

$$sim(f_1, f_2) = \mu_{f_1 \cap f_2}(def(f_1 \cap f_2)) \quad (1)$$

where \otimes and def are a t-norm operator [24] and a defuzzification function [34], respectively. We have restricted to the minimum t-norm to make the computation easier. The minimum of two triangular fuzzy membership functions depends on several cases, as illustrated in Figure 8. As defuzzification methods, we have tried the center of gravity (COG) and the Middle of Maxima (MOM). Note that in this case there is a single maximum (possibly zero), so the well-known largest (LOM), mean (MeOM), smallest (SOM) and middle of maxima defuzzification methods coincide. We have also tried with several other measures that we call the average (AVG)

$$sim(f_1, f_2) = 1 - \frac{\mu_{f_1}(a_{22}) + \mu_{f_2}(a_{12})}{2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 8: Different cases to compute the minimum of two triangular functions

and the minimum (MIN):

$$\text{sim}(f_1, f_2) = \min\{\mu_{f_1}(a_{22}), \mu_{f_2}(a_{12})\} \quad (3)$$

Similarity between two steps. We are now ready to define the similarity between two steps described by means of n features. Let $s_1 = \langle f_{11}, f_{12}, \dots, f_{1n} \rangle$ and $s_2 = \langle f_{21}, f_{22}, \dots, f_{2n} \rangle$ be two steps. Their similarity is an aggregation of the similarity between the n pairs of features:

$$\text{sim}(s_1, s_2) = @_{i=1}^n \text{sim}(f_{1i}, f_{2i}) \quad (4)$$

where $@ : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is an aggregation operator. Since we want all of the features to be similar, we use a t-norm, namely the product. Łukasiewicz t-norm collapses to zero very easily, and the minimum of a lot of aggregated values is not as discriminant as the product. In practice, we will work with very small lows but we checked in practice that they can be successfully managed as Java double numbers.

To avoid the fact the a single 0 value in the similarities between two features would make the whole result to be 0, in practice if for some feature we have $\text{sim}(f_{1i}, f_{2i}) = 0$, we replace the 0 value with a very small $\epsilon > 0$.

Classification of a new recording. Our classification algorithm is based on a voting-based scheme for the steps of a new recording $r_i = \langle s_{i1}, s_{i2}, \dots, s_{ip} \rangle$. That is, for each of the p steps of the new recording, denoted s_{ij} , we compute the similarity between s_{ij} and each of the known steps stored by our system. Each step of the new sequence will be a vote for one individual, the one obtaining the highest similarity, i.e., given

$$\operatorname{argmax}_{j=1, \dots, q} \operatorname{sim}(s_{ij}, s_{jk}) \quad (5)$$

the author of the step s_{jk} , the k -th step of the j -th recording, receives one vote. The individual with more votes will be the final result of the classification. In case of a tie, we retrieve the step with the highest value of $\operatorname{sim}(s_{ij}, s_{jk})$.

It is also possible to associate a fuzzy degree $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ to the classification result, and retrieve not only the winner individual but also a numerical value given by the ratio between the number of votes obtained by the winning individual and the total number of steps. This would also make it possible to retrieve the top- k individuals, decreasingly ordered by the classification degree.

Classification of new individuals. So far, our algorithm always returns an individual, the most similar one. However, it could be the case that the new sequence corresponds to a new individual, so the system does not have any previous steps stored and cannot succeed at recognizing it. In this case, it would be desirable that the system reported the existence of a new individual rather than trying to identify him/her.

For this reason, we have extended our algorithm with an additional step: an electoral threshold. The revised version of our algorithm retrieves the individual with more votes only if it received at least a percentage $\Theta \in [0, 1]$ of the votes, otherwise the system reports that the individual is unknown. It is also possible to associate a fuzzy degree to this decision: a winning individual with a percentage of votes $x < \Theta$, $x \in [0, 1]$, can be considered as a new individual with degree $\alpha = (\Theta - x) / \Theta$. Note that $x = 0$ implies $\alpha = 1$ and that α tends to 0 as x tends to Θ .

The problem now is how to select the value of Θ . A possible approach is to compute the percentages of correct classifications of the known people and of the new people, and find a tradeoff between both values using the ROC curve.

5. Evaluation

This section describes our experimental evaluation. Section 5.1 starts by describing existing datasets and a new one. Next, Section 5.2 discusses the results of our gait recognition algorithm, including the case of new individuals. Finally, Section 5.3 discusses how to obtain linguistic summaries of the biometric features of an individual.

5.1. Zaragoza dataset: OWL and RDF representation

Recall that each dataset is a collection of instantiated fuzzy ontologies, with respect to a schema ontology. To the best of our knowledge, there are only three existing datasets using Kinect to record people walking on straight lines or semi-circle paths, so we built a new one.

Kastanioitis et al. proposed the two first ones, denoted *Kas1* [22] and *Kas2* [22], where individuals walk a straight line. V. O. Andersson et al. proposed a dataset with lateral recordings using a moving camera, denoted *And1* [2]. For the purpose of this paper, we have built a new dataset, denoted *Zar2*. More details about the datasets can be found online, subject to legal compliance.⁴

- *Kas1* contains 30 individuals (15 males and 15 females). Each person contains 5 sequences and each sequence has between 1 and 5 steps. Data were acquired using a Microsoft Kinect V1 sensor.
- *Kas2* includes 30 individuals (17 males and 13 females). There are 10 sequences for every person. Each sequence has between 1 and 5 steps. Data were obtained using a Microsoft Kinect V2 sensor.
- *And1* includes 164 individuals. For each of them there are 5 or 6 sequences with a number of gait steps detected by our algorithm between 6 and 62. Data were recorded using a Microsoft Kinect V1 sensor.
- *Zar2* was built to increase the small number of individuals walking a straight line using Kinect v2 in *Kas2*. We had help of 91 volunteers walking a straight line, 34

⁴http://webdiis.unizar.es/~ihvdis/gait_recognition

women and 57 men with ages between 18 and 60. For each volunteer, 10 sequences were recorded in the experimental scenario, but a total of 8 sequences were discarded because they wore reflective clothes (such as leather jackets) that provided too many errors. Every sequence contains between 1 and 6 steps. Data were captured using a Microsoft Kinect V2 sensor, as described in Section 4.1.

Figure 9 shows the number of steps in the different datasets. We can see that most of the sequences in *Zar2* and *Kas2* contain between 3 and 5 steps, while most of the sequences in *Kas1* have between 2 and 3 steps. Because of the moving camera, sequences in *And1* have a much larger number of steps.

Figure 9: Number of steps in each dataset

Let us conclude with some statistical information. Table 1 shows the Kinect version (KV), total number of People (Pe), number of Sequences (Se), number of Steps (St) in each dataset (DS). Other metrics are illustrated like the average of Individuals (I), Frames (F), FuzzyDatatypes (FD), ClassAssertion (CA), ObjectPropertyAssertion (OPA) and DataPropertyAssertion (DPA) by sequence of a subject in a respective dataset. Overall, there are 2172 OWL instantiated files (so, 2172 sequences).

5.2. Evaluation of the classification algorithm

In this section we evaluate the accuracy of the classification, the accuracy of each type of features, the size of the datasets, and the running time.

Table 1: Statistics of OWL ontologies

DS	KV	#Pe	#Se	#St	I	F	FD	CA	OPA	DPA
Kas1	1	30	150	408	91	86	574	664	101	5180
Kas2	2	30	298	1058	107	101	749	856	122	7611
Zar2	2	91	902	3178	107	102	743	850	123	7619
And1	1	164	822	16745	621	598	4298	4919	746	35914

Classification analysis. To evaluate the performance of the classification, we considered 4 datasets (Kas1, Kas2, Zar2, And1), 4 defuzzification strategies (COG, MOM, AVG, MIN), and 2 training setups (20/80 and 80/20). For example, 20/80 means that we took 20% of the sequences of each individual as training data, and the remaining 80% was used as test data. Experiments were repeated 20 times and for each of them the selection of the sequences was random. We also include as baselines the best results computed by other authors: for Kas1 and Kas2 we include the results of the EK+RH method [21], and for And1 we include the results of the method in [23]; these are the best methods so far for straight lines and lateral recordings, respectively. We also include the results of a previous version of our work [4], using a different classification algorithm (nearest neighbour with Euclidean distance, restricting triangular functions to the average value) and only 12 biometrical features.

Table 2 shows the percentage of correct classification of the methods (average and, if available, standard deviation); please recall that details such as Kinect version, number of individuals, and number of sequences can be found in Table 1.

In datasets where individuals walk a straight line (Kas1, Kas2, and Zar2), our method outperforms EK+RH, the best method so far. For the best defuzzification strategy, the new method obtained an increment in the precision of 3–4%. In particular, our method was able to classify precisely all individuals of Zar2 for the case 80/20. Our method also outperforms our previous algorithm in [4]. However, for the dataset with lateral recordings using a moving camera, our system achieves worst classification results. This shows that our algorithm would require some changes to manage such datasets, but we leave this as future work. In particular, we would need different preprocessing techniques, as the type of noise is different, and possibly more flexible fusion operators than a t-norm (because every t-norm produces

Table 2: Classification results for various methods and training sample size (1-8)

Dataset	Method	Correct Classification Rate	
	Training/Test Size (%)	20/80	80/20
Kas1	EK+RH [21]	No data	95.67
	COG	88.37±1.88	99.33±1.37
	MOM	89±1.61	99.33±1.37
	AVG	86.88±1.01	97.17±1.22
	MIN	84.38±1.85	95.67±2.44
Kas2	EK+RH [21]	92.27	97.05
	[4]	No data	89.03
	COG	93.51±1.07	99.83±0.53
	MOM	94.01±1.05	99.66±0.71
	AVG	96.83±1.35	100±0
Zar2	MIN	94.92±1.26	99.66±0.71
	COG	98.34±0.54	100±0
	MOM	98.45±0.57	100±0
	AVG	97.86±0.95	100±0
And1	MIN	97.39±1.09	100±0
	[23]	No data	97.0±0.5
	COG	31.74±2.34	66.25±6.33
	MOM	33.75±2.80	68.56±4.97
	AVG	69.07±5.54	95.66±2.53
	MIN	61.54±6.17	93.84±3.57

a value which is smaller or equal than the minimum of the aggregated values, a single small value is enough to produce a global small value).

The best defuzzification strategy depends on the dataset. AVG is usually the best one (in Kas1, Kas2, and And1), but MOM is the best one in Zar2. In datasets where individuals walk a straight line there are not significant differences between the different defuzzifications,

Table 3: Results of each type of attributes on Zar2 dataset (20/80)

	Type								1-8
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
Size	4	16	27	21	33	60	25	25	211
COG	1.47±0.33	68.96±3.10	52.72±3.45	52.54±2.58	92.83±1.65	95.54±1.43	83.89±2.37	4.65±0.41	98.34± 0.54
MOM	1.53±0.40	72.43±3.63	61.30±3.33	56.37±3.54	93.79±1.40	95.94±1.45	84.46±2.72	7.10±0.94	98.45±0.57
AVG	0.87±0.28	59.57±2.70	35.70±3.11	44.29±2.83	71.14±3.11	94.72±1.23	67.75±3.47	6.29±0.97	97.86±0.95
MIN	0.70±0.23	50.92±2.52	20.99±2.47	36.13±2.27	62.36±3.30	90.80±1.67	59.83±4.44	5.33±0.98	97.39±1.09

but in And1 the differences between AVG and MIN, on the one side, and COG and MOM, on the other side, is really important (close to 30%).

Note that the sensor Kinect v2 (datasets Kas2 and Zar2) makes it possible to obtain very good results for the case 20/80, almost comparable to the case 80/20. This means that only 20 % of the data (i.e., 2 sequences for each individual) is enough as training data. However, for Kinect v1 (datasets Kas1 and And1), it seems preferable to use a 80/20 configuration (i.e., 4 sequences for each individual).

Note also that our system gets better results in Zar2 with 91 individuals than in Kas2 with 30 individuals. It has to be taken into account that Kas2 has been recorded with a sensor angle of 30 degrees on the direction of displacement. Therefore, the worst results in Kas2 might be caused by a problem of body self-occlusion, a problem previously reported in [27]. These results suggest that 3D sensor based gait recognition could be more appropriate in scenarios where the sensor is located frontally or combining information from different side placed sensors, that have vision on both sides of the body.

Features analysis. We considered the Zar2 dataset, 4 defuzzification strategies (COG, MOM, AVG, MIN), and a 20/80 scenario. Table 3 shows the results of each type of features (as defined in Section 4.2.4), and the number of features of each type. Experiments were repeated 20 times and we show the average and the standard deviation.

We can see that using all the feature types provides the best results. It is worth to stress that in a previous paper we proposed a feature selection step to reduce the number of variables [4], as some preliminary experiments showed that they did not have an influence in the results. However, the results with a high number of individuals show that when all

variables are considered, the precision of the classification is higher. Indeed, feature selection is more common in classification scenarios with a fixed number of labels to be classified, but in our case the number of classes increases every time a new individual enters the system.

We can also see that choice of the defuzzification strategy is quite significant. In general, when using only some type of features, COG and MOM perform better (recall that Table 2 concluded that AVG was usually the best defuzzification operator).

Using just some type of variables might provide good enough results. For example, type 6 has a higher precision than the method EK+RH (for the case of MOM). Then, if we add more attributes to the model, precision grows.

Indeed, we can obtain simpler models if needed for scalability reasons, although as we will see later the running time of our system seems very reasonable. Consider for example the case of MOM. While the full model has 211 attributes and a precision of 98.5%, a model based on type 6 has a precision only 2.5% smaller with between a third and a quarter of the attributes (60). Then, a model based on type 5 has a precision only 2% smaller than the model based on type 6 with about half of the attributes (33). Type 7 also provides a good precision (it is the third best type) with only 25 features, despite not having being widely used in the literature. Because type 7 features are those with less dependency of the height, this confirms again that how a person walks is actually useful to identify him/her.

Space and time analysis. Table 4 shows the space required by the OWL (OWL 2 ontologies in Manchester syntax) and TTL (RDF triples in Turtle syntax) versions of our fuzzy ontologies. We can see that OWL files require a much smaller size than TTL files. Indeed, OWL Manchester syntax is known to be a rather succinct syntax.

Table 4: Size (in MB) for each input format and dataset

Format	Dataset			
	Kas1	Kas2	Zar2	And1
OWL	111	304	939	4190
TTL	205	557	1750	8080

Table 5: Loading time (in s) for each input format and dataset

Format	Dataset			
	Kas1	Kas2	Zar2	And1
CSV	0.14	0.30	0.97	3.39
OWL	15	47	172	654
TTL	62	418	4267	16224

Next, we will detail some experiments to measure the running time. Firstly, we measured the starting time of the system; in particular, the loading time of the datasets in memory. This step is only performed once, during the initialization of the system. As a baseline, we also considered a CSV (text files with comma-separated values) version of the fuzzy ontologies that only stores data about the biometric features and not the raw Kinect data (as they are not used during the classification). The CSV version represents triangular fuzzy numbers by separately storing the average x and the standard deviation d .

Table 5 shows the results of the time (in seconds) needed to load the different datasets for different input formats: CSV, OWL, and TTL. Of course, the time depends on the number of individuals and steps, and so on the dataset. TTL requires much more time than OWL, as managing RDF triples using Jena, a database on Apache Jena Fuseki Server, and SPARQL queries was more costly than retrieving OWL 2 individuals and their data property values using the OWL API. Managing CSV is also significantly faster than OWL, so if the system is going to be restarted often, one could consider having a CSV copy of the datasets to speed the initialization up. Another suggestion is to split each OWL/TTL file into two files: one with the raw Kinect data, and another one with data about the biometric features, so that only the second one is loaded during the initialization of the system.

Secondly, we analyze the time (in seconds) needed to classify a new sequence using only features of type 6 (the type with a better precision) and using all of them. The experiment is repeated for each dataset and the results are shown in Table 6. On average, type 6 requires about a third of the total time, making it possible to have a good trade-off between running time and classification accuracy. It is worth to note that for very big datasets, such as And1,

the difference between the defuzzification methods is relatively significant, with AVG and MIN being the faster ones.

Table 6: Classification time (s) of one individual

Type	Method	Dataset			
		Kas1	Kas2	Zar2	And1
6	COG	0.03	0.07	0.10	5.49
	MOM	0.02	0.07	0.09	5.21
	AVG	0.02	0.06	0.12	4.42
	MIN	0.02	0.06	0.12	4.44
1-8	COG	0.07	0.22	0.30	17.37
	MOM	0.07	0.21	0.27	16.52
	AVG	0.06	0.18	0.35	14.59
	MIN	0.06	0.18	0.36	14.68

Evaluation of the discovery of new individuals. We have used Zar2 dataset to find an estimation of Θ : first, Zar2 dataset was split into a training set (80 %) and a test set (20 %); for any gait sequence of any individual p in the test set, the rate of votes obtained by p when there are other sequences of p in the training set, and the maximum rate of votes obtained by an individual q ($\neq p$) when all sequences of p are removed from the training set were calculated. The experiment was repeated 20 times with different training/test sets.

Figure 10 shows the ROC curve and the AUC (area under the curve). It is shown that the best founded electoral threshold Θ is equal to 0.917, and $AUC = 0.881$, that is, with this method it can be correctly classified the 88.1% of the sequences with a 95% confidence interval (0.874,0.889).

5.3. Linguistic summaries

Another advantage of combining fuzzy logic and ontologies is the possibility to compute linguistic summaries of the biometric features, i.e., providing linguistic descriptions

Figure 10: ROC curve: best threshold $\Theta=0.917$, AUC=0.881 (95% confidence interval (0.874,0.889))

of the features such as “very high” or ”low”, which are more informative for a human than the numerical values. Such linguistic descriptions are described with fuzzy membership functions. Although this is not currently used during our recognition algorithm, it illustrates that indeed our fuzzy ontology-based model increases the readability of the datasets and the interpretability of the results. For example, in addition to retrieving the most similar individual, our algorithm could also provide some explanations, for example, that both the author of the new recording to be classified and the recognized individual have a high step length and a low height (and similarly for other biometrical features).

To compute the linguistic values of the data properties of an ontology, we can use Datil⁵ tool. Datil supports learning fuzzy datatypes for fuzzy ontologies based on the values of the data properties [19]. A clustering algorithm provides a set of centroids, which are then used as the parameters to build fuzzy membership functions partitioning the domain of a values of the data property. Datil implements several unsupervised clustering algorithms such as *k-means* [26], *fuzzy c-means* [3], and *mean shift* [8, 9]. The tool also supports different input formats, including OWL 2 ontologies.

For illustrative purposes, we used Datil to obtain linguistic descriptions of the StepLength

⁵<http://webdiis.unizar.es/~ihvdis/Datil>

Figure 11: Five fuzzy datatypes associated to the StepLength biometric feature

feature, according to the values in the Zar2 dataset. Figure 11 shows five fuzzy membership functions and labels obtained after using k-means algorithm to compute 5 clusters ($k = 5$). Note that triangular is not the only type of membership function, there are also left-shoulder and right-shoulder functions. Figure 12 illustrates that a given subject has a length step 0.53 that can be considered as high with a degree 0.5453, computed as the degree of membership $\mu_{HighLengthStep}(0.53)$.

Figure 12: Degree of membership of one individual to StepLength

6. Conclusions and future work

In this work we have described a gait recognition system based on Microsoft Kinect and fuzzy ontologies. This has several possible applications, including security and medicine. Our system is rather quick at computing the recognition, making it suitable for real-world scenarios.

The main characteristic of our system is the use of fuzzy ontologies, which has several benefits: they are more robust against small changes in the values of the biometrical measures across different steps, and allow more detailed (by assigning a degree to the classification of a person) and interpretable results (thanks to linguistic summaries), and all the benefits of classical ontologies, such as providing automated reasoning (e.g., to check that there are no inconsistencies), more readable datasets, or making maintenance and data integration across applications easier.

We have proposed an architecture based on a schema ontology and several instantiated fuzzy ontologies including biometric features of individuals. Our approach makes it possible to represent both Microsoft Kinect V1 and V2 data and NuiTrack data, and all of the biometric features reported in the literature, plus some new ones.

We have also built a new dataset with 91 individuals (called the Zar2 dataset), discussed how to build the fuzzy ontology (enumerating several preprocessing techniques to improve the quality of the data), and showed how to use fuzzy logic to obtain linguistic descriptions of the biometric features.

Such fuzzy ontologies are used to train a novel gait recognition algorithm from Kinect data. The algorithm is based on step segmentation of the sequences, use of fuzzy logic to deal with the imprecision of the sensor, and a voting scheme to aggregate the values obtained for each step. Our system provides an answer in a short time after the data are loaded in memory. The results of our experiment show that our new method outperforms most of the existing algorithms in the case of individuals walking a straight line. We have also evaluated different defuzzification operators, with some differences in the accuracy depending on the dataset.

Additionally, we have evaluated our algorithm for lateral recordings using a moving camera. In this case, our algorithm usually performs worse and only the average defuzzification is comparable. We have also approached the problem of recognizing new individuals not

included in our knowledge bases, showing promising results.

There are many ideas for future work. Firstly, other Artificial Intelligence techniques could be applied to this problem to learn the biometric features. In particular, we think that neural networks and deep learning might be interesting: a preliminary step in this direction is described in [15].

Secondly, fuzzy logic theory provides a plethora of different operators that could be applied. For example, we could apply alternative defuzzification operators to compute the similarity between two features, or aggregation operators to compute the similarity between two steps. It seems particularly promising the use of alternative operators to compute the similarity between two sequences. When the number of steps is very high, as it happened in the dataset And1, a t-norm seems too strong, and other aggregation operators, such as a weighted mean or OWA [38], might be more suitable.

It could also be interesting to investigate the optimal number of sequences for each individual. If it is possible to keep the accuracy of the system, the smaller the training size, the faster the classification.

We noticed when building our dataset that reflective clothing affects the quality of the recordings. We would like to understand the limits of the sensor by studying whether different footwear (e.g., high heels vs. flat shoes) or clothing (e.g. wide clothes vs. tight clothes) in the training and test data has an impact on the classification. We expect some measures to keep having similar values (such as the length of the bones), but the global effect is still unknown.

Human gait is not exactly symmetrical. So far, although our fuzzy ontology stores the moving leg of a step, we do not take it into account to compute the similarity between steps. We think that the two most similar steps should correspond to the same leg, but we have not checked that empirically. This could allow to reduce the number of comparisons by half, as only steps of the same leg should be considered.

Because we retrieve the most similar step, we think that it should correspond to a step of the same leg (precisely because human gait is not symmetrical), but we have not really checked.

Last but not least, we have just started the study of techniques to identify new individuals. More sophisticated procedures involving the degree of similarity between the steps might be interesting.

Acknowledgement

We were partially supported by DGA/FEDER and projects CUD2017-17 (Centro Universitario de la Defensa) and TIN2016-78011-C4 (Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad). I. Huitzil was partially funded by Universidad de Zaragoza - Santander Universidades (Ayudas de Movilidad para Latinoamericanos - Estudios de Doctorado). Special thanks are to the volunteers that kindly participated in the recording sessions of the Zar2 dataset.

References

- [1] M. Ahmed, N. Al-Jawad, and A. T. Sabir. Gait recognition based on Kinect sensor. In *Real-Time Image and Video Processing 2014*, volume 9139, page 91390B. International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2014.
- [2] V. O. Andersson and R. M. de Araújo. Person identification using anthropometric and gait data from Kinect sensor. In *Proceedings of the 29th AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI 2015)*, pages 425–431. AAAI Press, 2015.
- [3] J. C. Bezdek. *Pattern Recognition with Fuzzy Objective Function Algorithms*. Advanced Applications in Pattern Recognition. Plenum Press, 2nd edition, 1987.
- [4] F. Bobillo, L. Dranca, and J. Bernad. A fuzzy ontology-based system for gait recognition using Kinect sensor. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Scalable Uncertainty Management (SUM 2017)*, volume 10564 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 397–404. Springer, October 2017.
- [5] F. Bobillo and U. Straccia. Fuzzy ontology representation using OWL 2. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 52(7):1073–1094, 2011.
- [6] N. V. Boulgouris, D. Hatzinakos, and K. N. Plataniotis. Gait recognition: a challenging signal processing technology for biometric identification. *IEEE signal processing magazine*, 22(6):78–90, 2005.
- [7] P. Chattopadhyay, S. Sural, and J. Mukherjee. Frontal gait recognition from incomplete sequences using RGB-D camera. *IEEE Transactions Information Forensics and Security*, 9(11):1843–1856, 2014.

- [8] Y. Cheng. Mean shift, mode seeking, and clustering. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 17(8):790–799, 1995.
- [9] D. Comaniciu and P. Meer. Mean shift: A robust approach toward feature space analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 24:603–619, 2002.
- [10] T. M. Cover and P. E. Hart. Nearest neighbor pattern classification. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 13(1):21–27, 1967.
- [11] B. Cuenca-Grau, I. Horrocks, B. Motik, B. Parsia, P. F. Patel-Schneider, and U. Sattler. OWL 2: The next step for OWL. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 6(4):309–322, 2008.
- [12] A. Davison. *Kinect Open Source Programming Secrets: Hacking the Kinect with OpenNI, NITE, and Java*. McGraw-Hill, 2012.
- [13] N. Díaz-Rodríguez, M. Pegalajar-Cuéllar, J. Lilius, and M. Delgado. A fuzzy ontology for semantic modelling and recognition of human behaviour. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 66:46–60, 2014.
- [14] N. Díaz-Rodríguez, R. Wikström, J. Lilius, M. Pegalajar-Cuéllar, and M. Delgado. Understanding movement and interaction: An ontology for Kinect-based 3D depth sensors. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Ubiquitous Computing and Ambient Intelligence (UCAmI 2013)*, volume 8276 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 254–261. Springer, 2013.
- [15] L. Dranca, Álvaro Lozano, R. Vigara, J. Bernad, I. Huitzil, and F. Bobillo. Técnicas de Inteligencia Artificial aplicadas al reconocimiento a través de la marcha. In *Proceedings of the VI Congreso Nacional de i+d en Defensa y Seguridad (DESEi+d 2018)*, page 258, 2018.
- [16] L. Dranca, U. López-de-Abetxuko, A. G. ni, A. Illarramendi, I. Navalpotro-Gómez, M. Delgado-Alvarado, and M. C. Rodríguez-Oroz. Using Kinect to classify Parkinson’s disease stages related to severity of gait impairment. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 19:471, 2018.
- [17] E. Fix and J. Hodges. Discriminatory analysis, nonparametric discrimination: Consistency properties. Technical Report 4, USAF School of Aviation Medicine, Randolph Field, Texas, 1951.

- [18] P. Hájek. *Metamathematics of Fuzzy Logic*. Kluwer, 1998.
- [19] I. Huitzil, U. Straccia, N. Díaz-Rodríguez, and F. Bobillo. Datil: Learning fuzzy ontology datatypes. In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems (IPMU 2018), Part II*, pages 100–112, 2018.
- [20] S. Jiang, Y. Wang, Y. Zhang, and J. Sun. Real time gait recognition system based on Kinect skeleton feature. In *Proceedings of the ACCV 2014 Workshop on Human Gait and Action Analysis in the Wild: Challenges and Applications*, volume 9008 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 46–57. Springer, 2015.
- [21] D. Kastaniotis, I. Theodorakopoulos, G. Economou, and S. Fotopoulos. Gait based recognition via fusing information from Euclidean and Riemannian manifolds. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 84:245–251, 2016.
- [22] D. Kastaniotis, I. Theodorakopoulos, C. Theoharatos, G. Economou, and S. Fotopoulos. A framework for gait-based recognition using Kinect. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 68(2):327–335, 2015.
- [23] N. Khamsemanan, C. Nattee, and N. Jianwattanapaisarn. Human identification from freestyle walks using posture-based gait feature. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 13(1):119–128, 2018.
- [24] E. P. Klement, R. Mesiar, and E. Pap. *Triangular Norms*, volume 8 of *Trends in Logic*. Kluwer, 2000.
- [25] G. J. Klir and B. Yuan. *Fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic: theory and applications*. Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1995.
- [26] S. P. Lloyd. Least squares quantization in PCM. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 28(2):129–137, 1982.
- [27] B. Müller, W. Ilg, M. A. Giese, and N. Ludolph. Validation of enhanced kinect sensor based motion capturing for gait assessment. *PloS one*, 12(4):e0175813, 2017.

- [28] M. A. Musen. The protégé project: a look back and a look forward. *AI Matters*, 1(4):4–12, 2015.
- [29] J. Pérez, M. Arenas, and C. Gutiérrez. The semantics and complexity of SPARQL. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2006)*, volume 4273 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 30–43. Springer-Verlag, 2006.
- [30] J. Preis, M. Kessel, M. Werner, and C. Linnhoff-Popien. Gait recognition with Kinect. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Kinect in Pervasive Computing*, pages P1–P4, 2012.
- [31] S. Staab and R. Studer, editors. *Handbook on Ontologies*. International Handbooks on Information Systems. Springer, 2004.
- [32] U. Straccia. *Foundations of Fuzzy Logic and Semantic Web Languages*. CRC Studies in Informatics Series. Chapman & Hall, 2013.
- [33] V. Torra and Y. Narukawa. *Modeling decisions - Information fusion and aggregation operators*. Springer, 2007.
- [34] W. Van Leekwijck and E. E. Kerre. Defuzzification: criteria and classification. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 108(2):159–178, 1999.
- [35] W3C. RDF Primer, 2004. <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-primer>.
- [36] W3C. OWL 2: Web Ontology Language Manchester syntax, 2009. <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-manchester-syntax>.
- [37] W3C. RDF 1.1 Turtle, 2014. <http://www.w3.org/TR/turtle>.
- [38] R. R. Yager. On ordered weighted averaging aggregation operators in multicriteria decision making. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, 18(1):183–190, 1988.
- [39] K. Yang, Y. Dou, S. Lv, F. Zhang, and Q. Lv. Relative distance features for gait recognition with Kinect. *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, 39:209–217, 2016.
- [40] L. A. Zadeh. Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(3):338–353, 1965.